

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL INNOVATION IN TRANSFORMING PHARMA TO THE NEXT NORMAL DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

MUHAMMAD JASRIF TEGUH^{1*}, NOERMIJATI NOERMIJATI², WAHDIYAT MOKO³ and ROFIATY ROFIATY⁴

¹Ph.D. Students, Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia. *Corresponding author Email: mujas84@gmail.com

^{2, 3, 4} Ph.D., Professor Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia.

Abstract

Digital innovation is the process of developing products or services, as well as improving and creating new business models using innovative digital technologies. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the pharmaceutical industry developed digital innovations along the value chain to continue contributing to producing products and services for society. This systematic review primarily aims to discover, evaluate, and synthesize research on digital innovations transforming the pharmaceutical value chain. The electronic database was used to search for digital pharma technology, innovation, and marketing articles, which were analyzed using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). The findings showed that the 24 research evaluated comprise three digital innovations in the pharmaceutical value chain, and each component meets the following criteria (1) digital product innovation in the R&D field, including artificial intelligence and machine learning, (2) digital process innovation in manufacturing and distribution such as the internet of things, digital twins, robotics, blockchain, and big data, and (3) digital business model innovation in the commercial sector including pharmaceutical omnichannel and digital marketing. It is expected that the practical implications of this research can serve as a guideline on the factors that influence digital pharma innovation in the future and their impact on achieving organizational performance, specifically in the next normal era.

Keywords: Digital innovation, digital technology, pharma industry, COVID-19

INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, the global economy has been rocked severally by recessions caused by changes in policies, and oil prices, including financial bubbles. However, the COVID-19 pandemic is related to the allocation of capital and the supply chain, specifically the disruptions of downstream and upstream (Papadopoulos et al., 2020). The pandemic is perceived as a health crisis, and a VUCA event is considered a disruption that elevates organizational and employees' responses to a new level, namely the "new normal" (Raghavan et al., 2021).

Organizational resilience was the key to business continuity during the pandemic. According to Nah and Siau (2020), business needs a flexible capacity to cope, adapt, and recover from a crisis. Furthermore, transformative activities require a superior capacity to reinvent the appropriate business model. COVID-19 has been a great accelerator in terms of triggering emerging modern technologies that have affected transforming lifestyles, work patterns, and business strategies (Srisathan and Naruetharadhol, 2022). Most companies strategically use

digital technology to deal with the impact of extreme events by connecting value-creation processes that ultimately increase competitiveness, productivity, and performance (Papadopoulos et al., 2020). Therefore, COVID-19 is perceived as a "catalyst" for the increased adoption of digitalization in handling business opportunities and challenges (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2021).

In the healthcare ecosystem, digital technology offered various contributions to handling the COVID-19 pandemic, which yielded a significant impact (Ting et al., 2020). Its rapid adoption led to new strategic frameworks and innovations (Secundo et al., 2021). Previous research highlighted the effect of digital technology on innovation agents, such as organizations or individuals (Nambisan et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Zimmerling and Chen (2021) stated that extreme events and technological developments are the main drivers of sustainable innovation. This includes flexible and sophisticated manufacturing capabilities, advanced personal protective equipment, and digital health technology.

New digital technologies which emerged due to the COVID-19 pandemic have altered the landscape of the pharmaceutical sector in recent years. Several current research investigated how to capture digital value creation in this industry. This entails focusing on specific processes related to developing new medicines and integrating product life cycle management as well as value chain models with operational implications (Kim et al., 2022). Meanwhile, Saha et al. (2022) examined the interactions between emerging technologies by incorporating and driving Pharma 4.0 to achieve a sustainable supply chain.

Previous research acknowledged the importance of digital technology in the pharmaceutical sector. However, the majority focused on digital initiatives in distinct parts of the pharmaceutical value chain. The research that focused on utilizing digital innovative development frameworks in the context of products, processes, and business models with respect to disruptive conditions is still limited, specifically in the post-COVID-19 era.

This present research aims to discover, evaluate, and synthesize preliminary investigations on digital pharma innovation as well as develop a transformation model of the pharmaceutical value chain in the normal era. Therefore, this led to the following research questions:

RQ1. What research has been conducted in the digital innovation field during the COVID-19 era regarding definition, digital technology, and research methodology?

RQ2. What is the future research agenda in the digital innovation field?

LITERATUR REVIEW

Schumpeter (1934) defined innovation as improved products, production techniques, organizational structures, recent market discoveries, and the input of new factors. Subsequently, its diverse types were examined based on two general criteria, the level of novelty and difference. Gatignon and Xuereb (1997) stated that some companies wishing to develop superior competitive innovation should possess a strong technological orientation. As digital technology develops, a new type of innovation has emerged, namely digital innovation.

It concerns developing and implementing innovative artifacts and related solutions based on re-using novel digital components (Fichman et al., 2014; Yoo et al., 2010).

Nambisan et al. (2017) defined digital innovation as the creation (and consequent change in) of market offerings, business processes, or models resulting from digital technology. According to Kurilova and Antipov (2020), companies recognize the need to increase competitiveness and strengthen its position in the market through innovation and the introduction of digital production. This influences its performance and outcome, changes business models, expands the market, and attracts new customers.

Digital innovation is a rapidly growing research area that reflects the deep and pervasive digitization and technological development process. The most recent research conducted by Hund et al. (2021) stated that it is the inherent creation or adoption and unlimited exploitation of newness, thereby adding value (for example, a product, service, process, or business model) through the incorporation of digital technologies.

The COVID-19 pandemic has fundamentally changed how companies, including pharmaceutical and healthcare, discharge their duties and collaborates to create new products, services, processes, and business models (Cohen et al., 2021). Innovations accelerate processes and potentially disrupt markets, existing revenues, and business models – as seen in the healthcare industry (Hoppe et al., 2022). Therefore, these companies must search for digital products or services, new combinations, and ways of production, as well as digital revenue creation or business models (Wiesböck and Hess, 2019).

Technological advances in the pharmaceutical industry have rapidly pioneered the scale of digitization in various aspects. This systematic review focuses on analyses carried out on digital technological development in the pharmaceutical industry. In addition, this is also followed by research that assessed the development of digital innovation across the pharmaceutical value chain, specifically during the COVID-19 era, starting from drug discovery R&D, manufacturing, and distribution to the commercial stage.

Arden et al. (2021) stated that digital technology innovation in industry 4.0 has the potential to transform pharmaceutical manufacturing and logistics platforms through digitization, autonomous systems, and robotics, as well as advanced computing. Incidentally, this starts with challenging traditional approaches, practices, and business models. The application of this technology has the potential to dramatically increase the agility, efficiency, flexibility, and quality of production in this industry. Specifically, the pharmaceutical supply chains, production processes, distribution, and inventory management tend to experience significant improvements with the aid of digital technology (Saha et al., 2022)

Meanwhile, in the healthcare sector, Biesdorf et al. (2021) reported that the digital health ecosystem has become increasingly relevant since the beginning of the pandemic. It was the impetus behind incorporating online and offline (omnichannel) offerings into an integrated healthcare ecosystem. The integration of core products and offering patients' journeys is perceived as important. Kim et al. (2022) designed a framework for implementing digital transformation in the pharmaceutical value chain model. This procedure can be integrated with

a product life cycle perspective, starting from the drug development stage to commercialization which has operational implications.

This research attempts to present digital innovation to the pharmaceutical industry by using concepts proposed by Wiesböck and Hess (2019) and incorporating it into the pharmaceutical value chain investigated by Kim et al. (2022). Several research on digital innovation in the pharmaceutical industry during COVID-19 are shown in Table 1.

METHODS

This research employed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guide (Page et al., 2021). The essence is to conduct systematic reviews because of its flexibility in guiding literature search and synthesis. The PRISMA model steps guide literature searches in various online electronic databases, including Google Scholar, Science Direct, IEEE Xplore Digital Library, PROQUEST, and Springer Link. Furthermore, this was based on the following search terms "Digital Pharma Technology", "Digital Pharma Innovation", or "Digital Pharma Marketing".

The articles published from the onset of COVID-19, from 2020 to August 2022, were selected. A total of 348 articles were obtained from the electronic databases, and the selected ones were filtered based on title, abstract, and full text. The research selection is required to meet the following inclusion criteria (1) written in English, (2) relevance, (3) published after the outbreak of the pandemic.

Some articles were excluded due to incompleteness, in the form of opinions, and not written in English. Citation chaining was performed to ensure that all relevant articles were included in this research. Afterward, 217 of them, including the duplicates, were removed, and the remaining 131 were checked for abstracts. A total of 85 incomplete articles, reprints, and letters to the editor were also eliminated.

After selecting relevant articles, the abstracts were independently assessed, and 46 were considered for review eligibility. Full-text articles were assessed for eligibility, 22 were removed, while 24 were considered in this present research.

Table 1: Literature Review on the interplay digital innovation in Pharma

Digital Innovation	Digital Technology	Value Chain	Research Method	Key Finding(s)	Reference
Digital Process Innovation	3D printing, Robotics, Internet of things	Manufacture and Distribution	Review	To manufacture individualized medical products, modernize pharmaceutical logistics, and deliver digestible drugs or diagnostic agents	Awad et al. 2021
	Digital Twin	Manufacture	Case Studies	Able to estimate accurate capacity requirements and visualize the resources required from the supply chain	Santos et al. 2020
	Blockchain technology, Machine Learning	Manufacture	LIC-IGL method	Validate blocks in the supply chain and provide abundant pharmaceutical sales information	Anitha and Srimathi, 2021
	Big data analytics, Machine Learning	Manufacture, distribution	Systematic literature review	Structured data analytics from machine learning generates information to address drug shortages and optimize inventory	Nguyen et al. 2021
	Blockchain	Manufacture and distribution	Review	Provide reliable quality control and assurance on inventory, suppliers, equipment, facilities, storage, transportation, and delivery conditions	Omidian and Omidi, 2022
	Internet of Things	Manufacture and distribution	Review	IoT increases the virtual visibility of the real-time pharmaceutical business, such as manufacturing, distribution, and consumption	Singh et al. 2020
Digital Business Model Innovation	Omnichannel pharmacy	Commercial	Cross-sectional, non-exploratory research	Omnichannel strategy for community pharmacies	Dhanraj et al. 2022
	Omnichannel Pharma Marketing	Commercial	Qualitative research approach	Omnichannel marketing provides a consistent, integrated, and personalized customer experience across the various channels or devices	Kaiponen, T. 2021
	Omnichannel, Electronic Detailing, Social-Media Marketing	Commercial	Review	Digital marketing investment and budget needed in the post-COVID-19 era to increase efficiency, profitability, and streamline functions	Adkonkar et al. 2022
	eWOM media sosial marketing	Commercial	Deductive approach quantitative	eWOM influences the decision to purchase OTC drugs online	Proença, 2022
	Media sosial marketing	Commercial	Review	Pharmacy organization's social media platforms, and doctors to provide innovative healthcare solutions	Mishra and Sanghvi, 2020.
	Artificial Intelligence	Commercial	Review	AI in pharmaceutical business development and marketing (Value pricing, Precision sales force messaging, Customer service, and engagement)	Veena, 2022

The research designs included are primarily digital pharma innovations used to run businesses related to the pharmaceutical value chain during the pandemic. The process for producing an ideal number of articles is depicted in the PRISMA flow chart, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: PRISMA diagram of this review

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on Table 1, 24 articles containing in-depth information about digital innovation were evaluated and used for data synthesis and analysis. In addition, the 10 elements of digital technology were found, and some were discovered to be repetitive. These were grouped into three types of digital innovation, which can also be categorized according to the value chain. Seven articles were included in the digital product innovation, 11 in the digital process innovation, and six in the digital business model innovation.

It was further discovered that the maximum number of digital innovation types concerning the pharmaceutical value chain used is 18. These originated from digital process innovation in the manufacturing sector. Furthermore, it was followed by 10 digital product innovation components in the research and development (R&D) sector. The minimum number was realized in the digital business model innovation, which amounted to seven in the commercial sector. The digital innovation component develops its model concept in the pharmaceutical value chain.

Table 2: Summarized information about digital innovation in the pharmaceutical value chain

Description	Digital Technology										TOTAL
	AI	IoT	ML	DT	3DP	BC	BD	RB	OMC	SMM	
Digital Innovation											
Digital Product Innovation	6		2		1		1				10
Digital Process Innovation	1	4	2	4	2	2	1	2			18
Digital Business Model Innovation	1								3	3	7
Value Chain											
R&D	6		2		1		1				10
Manufacture	1	4	2	4	2	2	1	2			18
Distribution		1			1	1	1				4
Commercial	1								3	3	7

The results also found three digital innovations in the pharmaceutical value chain, with each component, meeting the criteria. This consisted of, first, digital product innovation in the R&D field covering artificial intelligence/AI ($f=6$) and machine learning/ML ($f=2$). Second, digital process innovation in manufacturing and distribution, including the internet of things/IoT ($f=5$), digital twins/DT ($f=4$), 3D Printing/3DP ($f=3$), blockchain/BC ($f=3$), robotics/RB ($f=2$), and big data/BD ($f=2$). Third, digital business model innovation in the commercial sector, namely omnichannel/OMC ($f=3$) and social media marketing/SMM ($f=3$).

Subsequently, this digital technological component proposes an innovation model relating to the pharmaceutical value chain in the next normal era. This entails combining the three types

of digital innovation reported by Wiesböck and Hess (2019). It comprises digital products, processes, and business model innovations, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Digital innovation transformation along the pharmaceutical value chain

In this present research, digital innovation is defined as developing products or services, improving business processes, and creating new models using innovative digital technologies. Furthermore, for the benefit of future research, each component of digital innovation pharma is clarified.

1. Digital product innovation is related to the extent innovative digital technology based on customer data is used to produce new products and improve service quality.

Pharmaceutical companies need to invest in becoming a 'digital player' through the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in R&D, efficiency, production planning effectiveness, and drug development efforts.

2. Digital process innovation is related to the extent the optimized operational procedures are realized through production automation and the internet of things to execute distributive activities and customer relationship management.

In this case, pharmaceutical companies take advantage of the internet of things and robotics to boost their agility, efficiency, flexibility, and product quality. Digital twins are used to accurately estimate capacity requirements and visualize the resources required from the supply chain. Meanwhile, the blockchain provides reliable quality control and assurance on inventory, suppliers, equipment, facilities, storage, transportation, and delivery conditions.

3. Digital business model innovation is related to the extent to which companies adjust the portfolio through pharmaceutical omnichannel and develop new revenue models through digital marketing.

In this circumstance, pharmaceutical companies should invest and prepare budgets for developing omnichannel and digital marketing (including social media) to boost efficiency, profitability, and streamline functions, considering long-term growth in the next normal era.

CONCLUSION

This systematic review provides an overview of existing digital innovation research regarding key findings supporting its components and methodologies. In addition, 24 research concerning the use of digital technology in the pharmaceutical value chain, specifically carried out during the COVID-19 pandemic, was reviewed. Most of these research were conducted through reviews and case studies.

The findings showed that the research on digital innovation in the pharmaceutical industry during COVID-19 is still developing, although it has received attention from several international journals. It was discovered that 10 digital pharma technologies from 24 articles, including artificial intelligence, machine learning, the internet of things, digital twins, 3D printing, blockchain, robotics, big data, omnichannel, and social media marketing, were emphasized in this present research.

Applying this new technology promotes digital innovation in the pharmaceutical industry by developing a digital product, process, and business model innovation. It is perceived as a strategic benefit with a clear understanding of integrated goals in the pharmaceutical value chain. Furthermore, this present research proposes a model of "digital innovation in transforming pharma towards the next normal". Finally, it is expected that the findings of this systematic review will serve as a basis for future research. At the same time, its implementation along the pharmaceutical value chain is anticipated to increase its practical relevance. For example, exploring the antecedents influencing digital innovation in the pharmaceutical industry, such as digital organizational culture, business strategy, and digital capability. Its effect on the successful performance of pharmaceutical companies, specifically in the post-COVID-19 era, can also be examined.

This research has certain limitations, including (1) the use of multiple electronic databases may not fully cover all digital pharma innovation analyses. (2) It relies on specific keywords in the search stage, which may exclude some topics. (3) The nature of this present research is theoretical, therefore, further analysis is needed at the practical level.

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